

Archiving Dossier Narrative
Independent Crusaders Mapping Project, 1st Edition
Fordham University, Center for Medieval Studies

Project Catalogue record:

http://fordham.bepress.com/ddp_archivingdossier/3

Persistent Identifier DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.2562197

Current Project URL:

<https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project->

Launch Date:

July 15, 2017

Archive Date:

March 30, 2018

Narrative Section 1. Project Rationale and Scope:

Independent Crusading in the Twelfth Century

In the years between the “numbered” Crusades, a steady stream of pilgrims arrived in the Holy Land with the intention of offering their military services to the Latin States. According to the chronicler Fulcher of Chartres, this practice was customary by at least 1113,[1] and a range of evidence demonstrates that these individuals made a considerable impression both at home and abroad. Western scribes demonstrated an enthusiasm for recorded the deeds of a local magnate or patron who had devoted himself to a period of self-imposed exile in the Levant,[2] Christians writing in the East left us with the identity of numerous warriors who disembarked to fight,[3] and, on occasion, Muslim chroniclers turned their attention to these independent crusaders.[4]

Considering the prominence of crusading in recent medieval historiography, it is surprising that there has been little interest in this phenomenon. The expeditions known to history as the First, Second, and Third Crusades have been scrutinized by historians for centuries and continue to form the focus of a considerable body of scholarship. However, the small-scale expeditions of independent crusaders are presented as little more than an intriguing aside during studies of the larger ventures, stirring interest rather than taking centre stage in dedicated explorations.[5] This neglect can be attributed, in part, to the paucity and, in some cases, nature of surviving source materials. No chronicle equivalent to Ralph of Caen's *Gesta Tancredi*, which described the exploits of the first crusader Tancred, was produced to recount the deeds of Thierry of Flanders during his foray to the East in 1139,[6] nor did any offer extensive treatment of Charles the Good's time in the Holy Land during the first decade of the twelfth century,[7] and the source that dealt most comprehensively with King Sigurd of Norway's 1107–1111 campaign was written decades after the events it described.[8] Moreover, the study of these expeditions has been hindered, albeit inadvertently, by the interests and reservations of crusade historians. Specifically, a concern with definition has formed a prominent feature of crusade scholarship over the past five decades, and this has served, rightly or wrongly, to relegate independent crusades to a tangential interest of crusader studies.

The *Independent Crusaders* project is taking the first steps in exploring this understudied subject. We ask several questions of the surviving sources, but, more than simply a research project, our website is also a teaching resource that will introduce students to important questions in recent crusade historiography and aid in the development of research skills. This short introduction provides an overview of our project and the questions we intend to explore.

[1] Fulcher of Chartres, *Historia Hierosolymitana (1095–1127)*, ed. Heinrich Hagenmeyer (Heidelberg, 1913), 575.

[2] Galbert of Bruges, *De multro, traditione, et occisione gloriosi Karoli comitis Flandriarum*, ed. J. Rider, CCCM 131 (Turnhout, 1994), 31; Ekkehard of Aura, *Chronicon universale*, MGH SS, vi, 262.

[3] William of Tyre, *Chronicon*, ed. R.B.C. Huygens, CCCM 63 (Turnhout, 1986), 517 and 681; Fulcher of Chartres, *Historia Hierosolymitana*, 543–8.

[4] Ibn al-Qalānisī, *The Damascus Chronicle of the Crusades*, trans. H.A.R. Gibb (London, 1932), 106–7; Ibn al-Athīr, *The Chronicle of Ibn al-Athīr for the Crusading Period from al-Kāmil fī'l-ta'rīkh. Part 1: The Years 491–541/1097–1146: The Coming of the Franks and the Muslim Response*, trans. D.S. Richards (Aldershot, 2005), 152.

[5] A notable exception to this is Lee Manion's treatment of "privy crusading" in his recent exploration of the English crusading romance, albeit for a much later period: Lee Manion, *Narrating the Crusades: Loss and Recovery in Medieval and Early Modern English Literature* (Cambridge, 2014), ch. 2.

[6] William of Tyre, *Chronicon*, 681.

[7] Walter of Théroutanne, *Walteri vita Karoli comitis Flandriae*, MGH SS, xii, 540; Galbert of Bruges, *De multro*, 31.

[8] Snorri Sturluson, *Heimskringla: History of the Kings of Norway*, trans. Lee M. Hollander (Austin, 1967), 688–714. It should be noted that the *Heimskringla*'s account of Sigurd's expedition is derived from an earlier account, which is no longer extant and was also used in the *Morkinskinna*, and a range of skaldic poetry.

The Independent Crusaders Mapping Project provides a database, map, documents and pedagogical tools to inform audiences about expeditions undertaken by western European knights to the Holy Land and more specifically Jerusalem in the years between the papally sanctioned Crusades.

Narrative Section 2. Project Trajectory and Re-evaluation Rationale

The form of the project being archived here is the first iteration of the Independent Crusaders Mapping Project. It is the result of a number of decisions made in the course of the projects development. The project was always intended to include three parts, TEI encoded charters, a map visualizing data found in those charters, and a spreadsheet or database that structured the data found in the charters. Omeka was chosen as the publishing platform on the basis that it would provide a format for dealing with charters as individual objects in a collection, however, this ended up posing serious challenges as the platform was not well suited to handling the kind of textual TEI that characterized the charters. In addition the neatline mapping application associated with Omeka was scrapped in favor of Carto for its ease of use, however, new strategies had to be developed to ensure the Carto map would display through the omeka site. The final component, the structured data, never reached full functionality, the spreadsheets that were created as a result of the initial planning stages were too textual to be truly "structured," however, a more structured but less informative spreadsheet was created as part of the mapping component. Thus the current iteration of the project achieved the basic aim of displaying charters and a map that could inform the potential audience about "independent crusaders," but lacked the depth and data linkage that the development team hoped to achieve.

Narrative Section 3. Project Outcomes

The following products were a direct or indirect outcome from this project:

“Queerness of Space, Time and Text in the Independent Crusaders Mapping Project” Queer Encoding: Encoding Diverse Identities. NYU Center for the Humanities: New York, NY April 28th 2017.

“The Independent Crusaders Mapping Project: Addressing Medieval Sources Through Digital Mapping” Terra Digita Conference. Cornell University. Ithaca, NY November 2017.

Narrative Section 4. Tools Used

The project was built in the Omeka 2.0 content management system. The database was created in Excel 7.0. Spreadsheets. The departure map, inserted into the Omeka platform, was created in Carto.

Narrative Section 5. Web analytics

Web analytics from the project's launch in July of 2017 until March 2017 as uneven, with significant spikes after each presentation on the topic. See attached document (5a) for overall use patterns.

Narrative Section 6. Digital Objects

Please find PDF files of each webpage, the data sheet for project data (doc 6a), a sitemap, and a web recording of the project in action at the project's persistent identifier, at [10.5281/zenodo.2562197](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2562197)

Narrative Section 7. Project Preservation Plans; Copyright Clearance

We now have an MOU with Fordham University Library to host and maintain the contents of this dossier for ten years, until 10/2018 (doc 9a). Project metadata (doc 9b) produced in connection with the Fordham Library will make the data and project pages findable until this date. We have certified that all content conforms to appropriate copyright clearance laws. The project can be accessed, cited, and reused under a creative commons licence.

Section 8: Project Bibliography

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